

Early Performance and Energy Prediction of Neural Networks

Deployed on Multi-Core Platforms

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Motivation

Deployment?

Context

- ❖ Raise of interest for NNs deployed onto edge embedded platforms, and more specifically multi-core platforms.
- ❖ Early prediction of non-func. properties (e.g. latency, energy) of NN deployments is necessary to optimize execution and meet user defined constraints.

Challenges - How to propose fast yet accurate models with scalability in consideration of:

- ❖ Contention for shared resources,
- ❖ Computation/communication workload variability between deployments,
- ❖ Influence of power management strategies (e.g. clock gating).

Proposed modeling flow

→ The proposed modeling flow relies on calibration through measurements, analytical models and high level simulation to offer fast-yet-accurate evaluation.

Results

- ❖ 27 mappings of 4 NNs including 1 CNN tested with and without power management.
- ❖ Timing properties predicted with >97% accuracy, and energy properties with >95% accuracy.
- ❖ More information on the project can be found on our open source Git repository:

<https://gitlab.univ-nantes.fr/lenours-s/pssim4ai>

→ Example use of the modeling flow to perform Design Space Exploration (DSE) under performance and energy constraints:

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